

EVALUATION OF POTENTIALS FOR LOCAL TRANSFORM DOMAIN FILTERS WITH VARYING PARAMETERS

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ABSTRACT

We discuss the performance of a set of local transform domain filters, with respect to varying parameters. We perform Monte Carlo simulations of the filters over five different test images at different noise levels, and evaluate how much the selection of filter parameters affect the filter performance and how far their performances are from that of the ideal Wiener filter.

1 AN OVERVIEW OF LOCAL TRANSFORM DOMAIN FILTERS

Many of the discrete orthogonal transforms compact most of the energy of a signal into few high magnitude transform coefficients, whereas white noise spreads over all of the transform coefficients. This property helps to distinct noise from signal, and to suppress noise by simple operations in an orthogonal transform domain. Consider an observed image corrupted by additive, zero mean, white Gaussian noise, with variance σ_n^2 ,

$$g_{i,j} = f_{i,j} + n_{i,j}, \quad (1)$$

which can be expressed in an orthogonal transform T domain as

$$G_{w_1,w_2} = F_{w_1,w_2} + \nu_{w_1,w_2}, \quad (2)$$

where G_{w_1,w_2} , F_{w_1,w_2} , and ν_{w_1,w_2} are the transform coefficients of the noisy data, the original data, and the noise, respectively.

There might be different ways to implement filtering noise [1], and processing in transform domain is one of them that offers computational efficiency and easyness of adaptivity. The simplest processing in transform domain is "scalar filtering" [4] that assumes multiplication of transform coefficients of noisy data by certain weight coefficients η_{w_1,w_2} that can be regarded as transform domain response of a corresponding linear filter. Optimal values of the weight coefficients that minimize mean squared error between $f_{i,j}$ and its estimation $\hat{f}_{i,j}$ obtained by inverse transform T^{-1} of weighted coefficients $\eta_{w_1,w_2} G_{w_1,w_2}$

$$\hat{f}_{i,j} = T^{-1} \{ \eta_{w_1,w_2} G_{w_1,w_2} \}. \quad (3)$$

define a filter that is conventionally referred to as a Wiener filter and can be found as

$$\eta_{w_1,w_2} = \frac{S_{ff}(w_1,w_2)}{S_{gg}(w_1,w_2)}, \quad (4)$$

where $S_{ff}(w_1,w_2)$ and $S_{gg}(w_1,w_2)$ are spectral density functions of $f_{i,j}$ and $g_{i,j}$ measured as averages over corresponding ensembles of these functions for which the mean restoration error is evaluated. Wiener filtering can be applied both globally to entire images and locally to individual image fragments. Local filtering promises better adaptivity to local image properties.

In [5], transform domain local adaptive filters are studied in detail. They work in an orthogonal transform domain in a moving window, and nonlinearly modify the transform coefficients for obtaining an estimate for the central pixel. In local adaptive linear filtering, estimation of local spectra of noisy and original non noisy images is required from the observed noisy data. The simplest possible estimation is based on the following approximations:

$$S_{ff}(w_1,w_2) \approx \max\{0, S_{gg}(w_1,w_2) - \sigma_n^2\}; \quad (5)$$

and

$$S_{gg}(w_1,w_2) = |G(w_1,w_2)|^2. \quad (6)$$

Substituting the approximation Equation (5 and 6) into Equation (4) results in the *empirical Wiener filter* realization [5] :

$$\eta(w_1,w_2) = \max \left\{ 0, \frac{|G(w_1,w_2)|^2 - \sigma_n^2}{|G(w_1,w_2)|^2} \right\}. \quad (7)$$

In addition to Empirical Wiener filter, the following filter modification, called "rejective", or "hard thresholding", filter is proposed,

$$\eta(w_1,w_2) = \begin{cases} 1, & |G(w_1,w_2)|^2 \geq thr \\ 0, & \text{else} \end{cases}, \quad (8)$$

where the value of thr is associated with σ_n^2 .

These filters are implemented in a sliding window using an orthogonal transform as follows:

- Compute the spectral coefficients $\mathbf{G}^{(k,l)} = \mathbf{T}\mathbf{g}^{(k,l)}$ of the observed image fragment $\mathbf{g}^{(k,l)}$. $\mathbf{g}^{(k,l)}$ is a $K \times L$ frame from the observed image including the pixels $(k, l), \dots, (k + K - 1, l + L - 1)$.
- Multiply the obtained spectral coefficients by the filter coefficients $\{\eta_{i,j}\}$,

$$\widehat{F}_{i,j}^{(k,l)} = \eta_{i,j}^{(k,l)} G_{i,j}^{(k,l)}, \quad (9)$$

using Equation (7) or Equation (8).

- Inverse transform the output signal spectral coefficients
$$\widehat{\mathbf{f}}^{(k,l)} = \mathbf{T}^{-1}\widehat{\mathbf{F}}^{(k,l)}. \quad (10)$$
- The central pixel of the fragment $\widehat{\mathbf{f}}^{(k,l)}$ is the estimated value of the image at pixel $(k + K/2, l + L/2)$.
- Repeat the above steps by sliding the window over the image for $(k, l) = (1, 1)$ to $(k, l) = (M, N)$ where (M, N) are image dimensions.

2 PREVIOUS WORK

In our previous work [3], we compared local transform domain filtering to wavelet denoising, and observed that local transform domain filters perform better than wavelet denoising [2], which gained popularity recently. We also improved the performance of local transform domain filters by introducing averaging over overlapping windows. Let $W_{k,l}$ be the $K \times L$ window enclosing the pixels $(k, l), \dots, (k + K - 1, l + L - 1)$. The denoised value of pixel $(r_1, r_2) \in W_{k,l}$ by applying a denoising operator on the fragment of signal enclosed by $W_{k,l}$ can be expressed as

$$\widehat{f}_{r_1, r_2}^{(k,l)} = [\mathbf{T}^{-1}(\{\eta_{i,j} \cdot G_{i,j}\})], \quad (i, j) \in W_{k,l}. \quad (11)$$

We can have several estimates for pixel (r_1, r_2) by applying a denoising operator on several fragments of signal enclosed by all $W_{k,l}$ such that $(r_1, r_2) \in W_{k,l}$. An estimation of pixel (r_1, r_2) can be obtained by averaging over all such $\widehat{f}_{r_1, r_2}^{(k,l)}$;

$$\widehat{f}_{r_1, r_2} = \frac{1}{KL} \sum_{k=r_1-K+1}^{r_1} \sum_{l=r_2-L+1}^{r_2} \widehat{f}_{r_1, r_2}^{(k,l)}, \quad (12)$$

$$k = r_1 - K + 1, \dots, r_1, \quad l = r_2 - L + 1, \dots, r_2.$$

Averaging eliminates some of the artifacts introduced by hard thresholding (Equation (8)) in transform domain.

In this work, we address the following open questions:

- How does the noise suppression capabilities of the filters depend on the filter window size, the filter threshold, and the transform basis.

- What is potential denoising capabilities of the empirical filters, and how far are they from that of the ideal Wiener filter, which can be regarded as a benchmark for all linear filters.

We aim at investigating the above issues for empirical Wiener filter, rejective filter, and the filter obtained by averaging over overlapping windows.

3 EXPERIMENTAL SETTINGS AND RESULTS

We used five test images of different characteristics, two aerospace images, one MRI image, one piecewise constant image (computer generated), and the *Lena* image. The first four test images are presented in Figure 1. We performed three sets of Monte Carlo experiments on these images by using the following filters:

- ideal Wiener filter (Equation (4)),
- empirical Wiener filter (Equation (7)),
- rejective filter (Equation (8)),
- averaging over rejective filter (Equation (12)).

The aim of first setting was to evaluate the average performance of each filter with respect to varying threshold at different noise variances. The transform window size was set as 8×8 , and DCT was used. Standard deviations of the additive white Gaussian noise were set as $\sigma = \{15, 30, 60\}$. for the image dynamic range $(0, 255)$. The MSE was computed over the five test images. Figure 1 depicts the results of our first experimental setting. The bar which appears on the top of each plot shows the bound obtained by the ideal Wiener filter.

To summarize, we observed that

- Tested filters have the similar trend with respect to varying threshold for all test images, and all transform bases.
- Although the minimum mean square error achieved by the empirical Wiener filter is less than the minimum mean square error achieved by the rejective filter, rejective filter has a wider threshold region where the mean square error is close to the minimum, than that of the empirical Wiener filter.
- Averaging over rejective filter output always provides results closest to these achieved by the ideal Wiener filter.

In the second setting, we tested the above filters in DCT, Haar transform, and wavelet transform domains. We found that transform basis effects the performance more at low noise variances. Averaging decreases the gap between different transform bases. The computer generated *piecewise* image is used as a case study to

see the effect of transform basis. Piecewise continuous image can be fully represented by Haar transform, hence it gives better results when Haar basis is used.

Finally, the performance variation with respect to the transform window size is evaluated, in the third settings. 6×6 , 8×8 , and 10×10 window sizes were tested. When the noise variance was high, the filters with each window size performed equivalently. Figure 2 summarizes the results of this setting, with the rejective filter, when $\sigma = 15.0$, and DCT is the applied transform. It is observed that the optimum window size is different for different images. However, it is worth to note that the performance is not much sensitive to the window size, as can be observed from the figure.

4 CONCLUSIONS

We made extensive experimental studies for evaluating the potentials for a set of local transform domain filters. The ideal Wiener filter was used as a benchmark, and the empirical filters were tested on different images at different noise variances with varying parameters. We observed that, when filtering parameters are optimized, noise suppression capability of empirical filters is only slightly worse than that of the ideal Wiener filters.

References

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Figure 1: Test images. a) aero1, b) aero2, c)MRI, d) piecewise.

Figure 2: Average PSNR vs. threshold plots for filtered images. Noisy images are obtained by adding white Gaussian noise with a. $\sigma = 15.0$, b. $\sigma = 30.0$, c. $\sigma = 60.0$ (Solid line for empirical Wiener filter, solid-dotted line for rejective filter, dashed-dotted line for averaging over rejective filter).

Figure 3: PSNR vs. threshold plots for rejective filtered a. *aerospace*, b. *lena*, c. *MRI* images. Noisy images are obtained by adding white Gaussian noise with $\sigma = 15.0$ (Dashed-dotted line for 6×6 window, solid line for 8×8 window, and dotted line for 10×10 window). Threshold is multiplied by the square root of the window size.